

Borderlands, Resources and Interpolis Disputes. Remarks on the Areas of Joint Exploitation in the Hellenistic Peloponnese

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1. Introduction*

This paper delves into a special group of border areas that were subject to joint exploitation by neighbouring communities. Particular attention is paid to the borderlands known as κοινὰ χῶραι (« common regions ») attested by a handful of inscriptions that preserve some details about their origins and status.¹ Indeed, evidence about these sub-regions substantiates the evocative image of ‘multiple territories’ where frontiers, people, interests, experiences and cultures come into contact, compete (either in a peaceful or hostile manner) and sometimes conflate one into another.² In this respect, the Hellenistic Peloponnese stands out as an area of inquiry of the utmost interest, providing as it does a limited but varied body of evidence. In general terms, a border demarcation from central Arcadia, the contents of which will

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1. A scholarly overview on this subject is still lacking. See Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 39-40; Rousset, 2003-2004, p. 119-121; cf. Rousset, 1994, p. 124.
2. An earlier version of this paper has been prepared for the conference *TeMAES 4. Territoires multiple: façonner les régions dans le monde grec*, organised by Clémence Weber-Pallez and held at the University of Toulouse II – Jean Jaurès on June 6th, 2023. I am indebted to the organiser and all the members of the research group *TeMAES* (Stefania De Vido, Arianna Esposito and Airton Pollini) for the kind invitation to the conference and the permission to publish in advance some preliminary thoughts set forth in Toulouse.

be touched upon in this paper, proves that the establishment of the *koinai chorai* in the Peloponnese dates back at least to late Classical times. However, explicit references to the Peloponnesian *koinai chorai* surface only in two inscriptions from the 2nd century Argolid, while the existence of other areas subject to joint exploitation can be inferred from the dispositions of two more texts, where the terms of resource sharing are admittedly elusive or simply different from those of a ‘ordinary’ common land.

One of the peculiarities of these border areas lies in the joint exploitation of their resources by neighbouring *poleis*. As Sylvian Fachard has concisely observed, « [e]xploiting resources in a foreign chora was not tolerable: it would have been considered as a hostile action, excruciating for a polis and its citizens ».³ As a matter of fact, inscriptions demonstrate that individuals or communities could be granted access to foreign territories and take advantage of the resources available in there.⁴ On the one hand, proxeny decrees prove that a community (no matter whether *polis* or *koinon*) could bestow on foreigners privileges like grazing rights (ἐπινομία)⁵ or the rights of wood exploitation (ἐπιξύλια).⁶ In these cases, provisions about the geographical limits of the concession remain vague, which leads scholars to believe that these privileges were virtually effective on the entire territory of the granting community.⁷ On the other hand, there are cases in which two *poleis* reach – or are forced to reach – an agreement (ὁμολογία) on the ways of exploitation of a given territory, which may thereafter be declared a *koine chora*. Sometimes the texts of such agreements outline the limits of the areas subject to joint exploitation, whereas in other cases they only provide choronyms, allowing us to identify the territories at issue very roughly. As for the *koinai chorai*, in most cases their status was established or re-asserted by a third party in order to prevent or settle border conflicts.⁸ In Hellenistic times, the involvement of federal authorities surfaces in one way or another in the available evidence and this leads us to wonder whether federal intervention stems from the lines of a specific policy implemented by Greek *koina* or whether it was simply intrinsic to the membership to a federal state.⁹

These pages, however, do not aim at investigating in full all the questions raised by the study of the *koinai chorai* and other borderlands subject to joint exploitation. As a preliminary approach to the topic, which will be investigated more extensively in the framework of the ERC Project *FeBo: Federalism and Border Management in Greek Antiquity* (P.I. E. Franchi, University of Trento), this paper will rather focus on the geography of these sub-regions and the natural resources available in there.

3 Fachard, 2017, p. 20.

4 In fact, Fachard does not ignore the complexity of borderlands in terms of organisation, ownership and resources. In his study on the Attic-Boeotian frontier, he shows that the scholarly view that looks at the border areas as territories almost uninhabited and, as it were, nearly deregulated must necessarily be blurred and reassessed on a case-by-case basis (Fachard, 2017, p. 25-27).

5 Marek, 1984, p. 147-149; Hodkinson, 1988, p. 51-53, 62-63; Chandezon, 2003, p. 351-389.

6 Rousset, 2010, p. 48-50. On the timber trade in the Peloponnese, see Mackil, 2013, p. 275-276.

7 See Mackil, 2013, p. 258-260, for the privileges exercised by *proxenoi* throughout the territories of Boeotia and Achaia.

8 Cf. Rousset, 1994, p. 122-123.

9 For the economic weight of some sub-regions like the *koinai chorai*, see Mackil, 2013, p. 257.

2. The *koinai chorai*: some attempts of definition

In his report of a course taught at the École Pratique in 2003-2004, Denis Rousset has defined the « régions communes » (κοινὰ χῶραι) as « zones indivises et appartenant simultanément à deux cités, sises sur leurs frontières, et interrompant quelquefois le tracé de la ligne-frontière ».¹⁰ Rousset's definition followed some observations made by Giovanna Daverio Rocchi in the book *Frontiera e confini nel mondo greco*: according to Daverio Rocchi, a *koine chora* is « uno spazio sottoposto ad un complesso di norme specifiche e affidato all'amministrazione congiunta delle poleis che separano »,¹¹ and its establishment « è sollecitata da imperativi economici, di portata locale ».¹² Indeed, economic matters are key factors for understanding the reasons behind the establishment of a *koine chora*. Nevertheless, while it is undoubtedly true that such *economic imperatives* corresponded to local interests, it deserves to be emphasised that the stabilisation of the disputed border areas could have political repercussions on a macro-regional scale.¹³ Federal states were crucial players in the Hellenistic Peloponnese: their stability heavily depended on the preservation of the internal balance of power, as well as the containment of conflicts between members. In some cases, federal authorities – the Achaean *koinon*, the Aetolian *koinon* and the Arcadian *koinon* – intervened to regulate the joint use of contested border territories.¹⁴ In other cases, the mediation of the *koinon* remains in the background, even if it may be inferred from the actors and/or circumstances referred to.¹⁵

Admittedly, the body of evidence is not abundant, and this poses some still insurmountable obstacles to the study of the real terms of management of the common regions. Epigraphical evidence (both from within and outside the Peloponnese) reveals an array of dispositions regulating the joint exploitation of borderlands, even without yielding to us the basic tenets for developing a full-fledged and consistent pattern of a *koine chora*.¹⁶ As for many other topics related to the study of the ancient world, the development of reliable models is heavily hampered by the scantiness, conciseness and fragmentary nature of our evidence. A crucial point that has increasingly challenged scholars, for example, is the question of ownership *of* and *within* the *koinai chorai*. As emerged above, Rousset regards them as *indivisible ownership/property of two cities*, whereas Daverio Rocchi argues for their *joint administration by the poleis at their borders*. Accordingly, the attribute κοινός is supposed to encapsulate implications of juridical, political and economic nature at one time: these territories are

10 Rousset, 2003-2004, p. 119.

11 Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 39.

12 Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 40.

13 As Fachard has pointed out, exploiting a (border)land is a strategy to possess and control it (Fachard, 2017, p. 37-38).

14 Mackil, 2013, p. 313-314 underestimates the role of the Achaean *koinon* in the resolution of the disputes amongst its members.

15 Ager, 2015, p. 476-480. For the case of the Achaean *koinon*, see also Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 119-129 and Rizakis, 2015, p. 128-131.

16 For some criticism to established patterns relating to fringe areas (*eschatiai*), see Giangiulio, 2001 (esp. p. 341-343).

therefore jointly owned, jointly managed and jointly exploited.¹⁷ One may cast some doubt whether this is how the situation stood. In this respect, the contribution of epigraphical sources is all but unambiguous, as are also some positions assumed by scholarship in the past.¹⁸ Ultimately, the very term κοινός, which implies *per se* a plurality of agents, does not enable us to solve the dilemma between ownership or possession of a *koine chora* and it shows that even an accurate terminological examination of epigraphical phrasing is far from being conclusive.¹⁹ The picture of the common regions as *copropriété indivise de deux cités* must be reconsidered, as Cristina Carusi has pointed out while emphasising the existence of private estates (κτήσεις) within the *koine chora* between Troezen and Methana.²⁰ At the moment, at any rate, we are concerned with four inscriptions from the Hellenistic Peloponnese, to which a late Classical text from Arcadia can be added. By tackling the subject from a geographical point of view, this paper will dwell on the location of these territories, their denominations and, finally, the resources they had to offer.

3. The location of the *koinai chorai* in the Peloponnese

If we focus on the information provided by inscriptions, Messenia and Argolis stand out as the two Peloponnesian regions more concerned by the presence of *koinai chorai*. Apparently, the Messenian evidence is slightly earlier than that from Argolis and pertains to territories lying along the borders with Arcadia. In a way, this connection with Arcadia sheds a different light on the documentation so far available since the earliest epigraphical evidence from the Peloponnese concerning the *koinai chorai* comes from central Arcadia and goes back to late Classical times. The fragment of a border demarcation between Orchomenos and another unknown Arcadian *polis* (*IPark* 14) is usually dated to between 369 and 361, although Rousset has argued for a later chronology.²¹ As in other cases, this text is informed by the application of natural reference points,²² and it is therefore not surprising that the border sub-regions proclaimed common (κοινὰ ἀμφοτέροις) are called Παδόεσσα

17 See already Wilhelm, 1948, p. 69.

18 See, for example, Skydsgaard, 1988, p. 80 (« Finally, if one focuses on the borderland between city states a common pasture is often found. We have already noticed Mount Cithaeron [...]. A similar no man's land existed on the Mount Parnassus and caused the outbreak of the Corinthian War »); Chaniotis, 1999, p. 198 (« Instead of setting boundaries for a disputed frontier region, the cities involved agreed to use these areas in common, as *koinai chorai* »); Rousset, 2003-2004, p. 121 (« Les régions communes, à la différence des zones désertes ou neutres, sont la copropriété indivise de deux cités, et se caractérisent par la possibilité d'une exploitation économique »); Daverio Rocchi, 2016, p. 73 (« Interest in exploiting woodland resources compelled the *poleis* to making agreements in order to subject these middle-lands [altogether or partly] to a regime of shared use [*koinai chorai*] »).

19 Chaniotis, 2004, p. 187-190 with the remarks of Fachard, 2017, p. 26.

20 Carusi, 2005, p. 109; cf. Fachard, 2017, p. 26.

21 369 BCE: Plassart, 1915, p. 62-69. 369-361 BCE: Dušanić, 1978, p. 348-351; Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 96-99; Thür, Taeuber, 1994, p. 124-129. For a later chronology, see Rousset, 2003-2004, p. 121. For the involvement of the Arcadian *koinon* in the dispute, see Mackil, 2013, p. 314.

22 Rousset, 1994, p. 117-118.

(literally « conifer forest » or « mahaleb cherry forest ») and Ἀρία (« the oak forest »).²³ Their respective positions rely on the identification of the *polis* sharing the border with Orchomenos (Methydrion or Torthyoneion), even if the assumption that they were located on the (south-)western borderlands of Orchomenos is probably not far from being true.²⁴ As far as we can tell, however, the actual jurisdiction of the *koinai chorai* near Orchomenos still seems to be uncertain: indeed, the formulation κοινὰ ἀμφοτέροις does not clarify whether Παδόεσσα and Ἀρία are jointly owned or only accessible to both for exploitation.²⁵ Interestingly, the same uncertainty affects the status of the border area mentioned in our earliest evidence from the Hellenistic times: the ὁμολογία between Phigaleia and Messene.²⁶

The agreement between Phigaleia and Messene (*IG V 2*, 419) is usually assigned to around 240 BCE and was concluded under the auspices of the Aetolian *koinon*.²⁷ The inscription, which has been unearthed at the ancient site of Phigaleia (western Arcadia), includes an excerpt from a decree by the Messenians acknowledging the rights of exploitation of one region by the Messenians and Phigaleians (τὰν δὲ χώραν καρπιζέσθαι ἑκατέρως, τὼς τε Μεσσανίως καὶ τὼς Φιαλέας).²⁸ Strictly speaking, this is one of the cases in which the existence of a *koine chora* may be inferred only by an interpretation of the text phrasing, and not by a straightforward statement made in the inscription.²⁹ Moreover, the decree of the Messenians adds that *the* region (τὰν δὲ χ[ώραν]) shall be exploited by both communities in the same ways as they did at the time (καθὼς καὶ νῦν καρπιζόμεθα).³⁰ Then, there is no mention of a *koine chora*. The general tone of the clauses and the somewhat elliptic phrasing undermine a full comprehension of this passage and, especially, the original sense of ἑκατέρως.³¹ In this regard, it is hard to ascertain how Phigaleians and Messenians could

23 Plassart, 1915, p. 56, 82; Dubois, 1986, II, p. 141-143.

24 While scholarship usually identifies Methydrion as the polis sharing the borders with Orchomenos (Plassart, 1915, p. 69; Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 97), Slobodan Dušanić rather opted for Torthyoneion (Dušanić, 1978, p. 351-355).

25 Cf. Rousset, 2002, p. 176 (« Sur les confins des cités grecques, la stricte définition d'une ligne-frontière pouvait en effet expressément laisser place, en tel point d'une délimitation, à des zones communes, comme on le voit sur les confins d'Orchomène d'Arcadie [...]. On peut donc concevoir que le territoire d'une cité ait été ici limité par une ligne, tandis qu'ailleurs il se perdait dans une zone laissée à l'usage de tous »).

26 See Robert, 1960a, p. 534; cf. Rousset, 1994, p. 123-125.

27 For some other editions and commentaries, see, for example, Schmitt, 1969, p. 182-185 (= *StV* III, 495); Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 162-164; Thür, Taeuber, 1994, p. 295-301 (= *IPArk* 28); Ager, 1996, p. 119-124 (No. 40); Magnetto, 1997, p. 230-237 (No. 38); Saba, 2020, p. 170-175 (No. 39).

28 *IG V 1*, 419, ll. 13-15.

29 See, for example, Robert, 1960a, p. 534; Thür, Taeuber, 1994, p. 300; Ager, 1996, p. 123; Magnetto, 1997, p. 234; Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 47-48.

30 *IG V 2*, 419, l. 15. Kienast, 1964, p. 62 translates *IG V 2*, 419, ll. 13-15 implying that the Messenians owned the region and they allowed the Phigaleians to exploit it jointly (« Das Land aber sollen sie beide nutzen [...], die Messenier und die Phigaleer, wie auch wir [d. h. die Messenier] es jetzt nutzen »). Indeed, the subject of καρπιζόμεθα is not obvious.

31 The ambiguity of *IG V 2*, 419, ll. 13-15 was pointed out by Robert, 1960a, p. 234 (« les deux peuples de Messène et de Phigalie [...] exploitent en commun un territoire, il « n'appartient » à aucun des

together exploit a well-defined plot of land *each to its own benefit*.³² Uncertainties affect the identification of the disputed territory too, since the remainder of the Messenian decree lacks any topographical detail. As a matter of fact, the inscription merely aims at transmitting a set of measures taken by the *demos* of Messene in favour of the Phigaleians.³³ Accordingly, the addition of other information of minor relevance may have not been in line with the purposes and summary nature of the text itself. This does not mean, of course, that the boundaries of the *chora* at stake (presumably at the origin of the dispute)³⁴ were not defined elsewhere. Sheila Ager, for instance, associates with the same contested borderland two more fragments of boundary delimitations which have been found in Messene and date back to the 2nd century BCE.³⁵ However, there is no compelling indication in both fragments suggesting some sort of overlap with the border region at stake in *IG V 2*, 419,³⁶ which is likely to stretch out along the banks of the river Neda.³⁷ In connection with the *homologia* from Phigaleia and the *χώρα* mentioned therein, it should be stressed that the intervention of the Aetolians and their supervision of the agreement were likely geared towards the stabilisation of an area of strategic importance for the League, especially in a moment when the *koinon* was seeking to

deux [...], ou ils décident, dans leur accord, d'exploiter chacun leur territoire, sans soulever les questions de propriété qui les divisent au sujet de leurs frontières »). Gawantka, 1975, p. 67 n. 60 has stressed the differences between *ἐκάτερος* and *ἀμφοτέρως*, still without ruling out the existence of a *koine chora* along the borders between Phigaleia and Messene (cf. Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 162-163 n. 1; Thür, Tæuber, 1994, p. 300). As it happens, the general formulations of *IG V 2*, 419, ll. 13-15 have led some scholars to raise doubts on the very existence of this common borderland. According to Buraselis, 2002, p. 228, this passage is to be regarded as a diplomatic formula pointing to reassert the exploitation rights of each community *over its own territory* (see now Saba, 2020, p. 172 n. 19). Indeed, the point made by Kostas Buraselis deserves some further thoughts, which must however reconsider the entire passage in its epigraphical and historical context.

- 32 Cf. Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 162-163 n. 1. In fact, one may wonder if *ἐκάτερος* could imply the distribution of personal properties – of both Phigaleian and Messenian citizens – within the *χώρα* itself (cf. Sartre, 1979, p. 216: « Ce qui importe pour nous ici, c'est de constater que la cité se conduit à l'égard de sa frontière comme un propriétaire en ce qui concerne les limites de son champ. D'ailleurs, il est probable que la cité ne fait, le plus souvent, dans ces querelles, qu'épouser la cause d'un citoyen ou d'un groupe de citoyens propriétaires aux frontières »; Fachard, 2017, p. 24: « Greek borderlands, when exploited and inhabited, are areas of interactions at the public and *private* levels. »; my emphasis). The presence of private domains in a *koine chora* is certain for the *homologia* between Troezenians and Arsinoeans/Methanians (*SEG* 55, 425, l. 25; see Carusi, 2005, p. 109 and below). It is worth observing that the prescription preceding ll. 13-15 concerns the drafting of a *συμβολά* intended to settle private controversies (*IG V 2*, 419, ll. 12-13: *ποιήσασθαι δὲ καὶ συμβολάν, ἃ[νπερ δοκεῖ] ἀνφοτέρας ταῖς πόλεις* [« they shall also establish a judicial agreement that pleases both cities »; transl. S. Saba]; cf. Gauthier, 1972, p. 366-368; Ager, 1996, p. 123).
- 33 Noteworthy is most of all the exchange of the *isopoliteia* and *epigamia* (see Gawantka, 1975; Vêrilhac, Vial, 1998, p. 68-69, 71-82; Saba, 2011, esp. p. 103-106; Saba, 2020, esp. p. 170-175).
- 34 See already Ræder, 1912, p. 95-97 (No. LI); Tod, 1913, p. 9-10 (No. V-VII); Gawantka, 1975, p. 114 n. 46. Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 164 has raised doubts on this interpretation.
- 35 *IG V 1*, 1429 and 1430. See Ager, 1996, p. 123.
- 36 Magnetto, 1997, p. 236 n. 8; Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 47-50.
- 37 Strab. VIII 3, 22.

expand its influence and its web of alliances in the southwestern Peloponnese.³⁸ In this sense, the efforts to promote good relationships between Messenians and Phigaleians, two of the major Aetolian allies in the Peloponnese, should be regarded as attempts by the Aetolians to lend more solid ground to their overseas power.³⁹

Evidence of a later controversy along the Arcadian-Messenian border has come to light in an epigraphic *dossier* recording a dispute between Messene and Megalopolis, which has been unearthed in the *temenos* of Messene at Messene and is still partially unpublished (*SEG* 58, 370).⁴⁰ The inscription is likely to date to the aftermath of the capitulation of Messene and the restoration of the *polis* to the Achaean *koinon* (ca. 180-175 BCE).⁴¹ The history of this long-standing conflict has been outlined by Nino Luraghi and Anna Magonetto, and there is no need to dwell on it at length here.⁴² On the whole, the issue at stake was the ownership of four territories (Ενδανικά, Πυλανικά, Ακρειᾶτις, Βιπειᾶτις), two of which (*Akreiatis* and *Bipeiatis*) appear to have been the main point of contention.⁴³ The sub-regions called *Akreiatis* and *Bipeiatis* belonged to a larger *χώρα* that was eventually recognised as Messene's property after the sentences had been issued by seventeen ἀγεμόνες of the Achaean League (ll. 15-43) and a board of 147 judges from Aigion (ll. 50-64).⁴⁴ Yet, the Messenians had earlier allowed the Megalopolitans to exploit this area in return for a compensation of 50% of the crop (the καρποί in ll. 66, 69), and this has been regarded as a special instance of *koine chora* or, borrowing a word used in the inscription, a 'mesokoine chora'.⁴⁵ Some years ago, Yannis A. Pikoulas published a paper aiming at re-establishing the geographical backdrop of

38 Larsen, 1968, p. 203, 206-207; Scholten, 2000, p. 116-123; Mackil, 2013, p. 116-117.

39 See Grainger, 1999, p. 159-161; Kralli, 2017, p. 278-281.

40 Some preliminary notes on the text were provided in Themelis, 2008. See also Arnaoutoglu, 2009-2010; Thür, 2012 and D. Rousset in *BE* 2013, No. 153-154.

41 Habicht, 2012.

42 Luraghi, Magonetto, 2012.

43 Luraghi, Magonetto, 2012, p. 529.

44 A commentary on the different stages of this arbitration can be found in Luraghi, Magonetto, 2012, p. 525-533. The last phase of this arbitration, which was resolved by a panel of six Milesian judges, focused on the validity of the fine imposed by federal *damiourgoi* (see Luraghi, Magonetto, 2012, p. 535).

45 The expression *koine chora* does not properly mirror the situation at the borderlands between Messene and Megalopolis (for a different view, see Youni, 2012, p. 326). There can be no doubt that what results from the *dossier* is definitely the Messenian ownership of the contended *χώρα* and the existence of previous (formalised?) agreements between Messene and Megalopolis about some sort of joint exploitation of the *Akreiatis* and *Bipeiatis* (cf. Thür, 2012, p. 299-300). Accordingly, the 'semi-common' nature of both sub-regions takes shape only in relation to the exploitation rights in force over them, not in relation to their ownership (see esp. Thür, 2012 and Youni, 2012). One might wonder whether this twofold facet of the Messenian *chora* (exploitation vs. ownership) discloses in fact another possible sense of μεσόκοτος, being the term not only tied to the produce of these borderlands but extending somehow to the status of the contested *χώρα* (on μεσόκοτος, see Luraghi, Magonetto, 2012, p. 533-534 n. 78). What is published from this long text does not say anything about the circumstances resulting in this Messenian-Megalopolitan agreement on the joint exploitation (cf. Youni, 2012, p. 321).

this dispute.⁴⁶ However, Pikoulas' attempt while often grounded on questionable inferences nonetheless drew attention to the importance of the historical topography as well as the outcome of archaeological surveys. As a matter of fact, looking at the content of the *dossier*, one can argue that all the disputed territories lay relatively close by the Megalopolitan borders (if not properly in an immediate contiguity with it) and one of them, the *Akreiatis*, certainly derives its name from the presence of heights in the territory itself (ἄκρα).⁴⁷ Then again, except for the *Endanika* (the territory of Andania), all other toponyms are nearly unattested,⁴⁸ which makes it extremely difficult to pinpoint them on a map. Finally, it must be stressed that the size of these border areas as well as the location of one in relation to another remain matters of speculation, unless the unpublished part of the inscription provides more details in this respect.⁴⁹ Finally, it may be tentatively concluded that at least the *Akreiatis* and *Bipeiatis* appear to be closer to the Megalopolitan borders than the *Endanika* and *Pylanika*,⁵⁰ and the *Akreiatis* is likely to be located somewhere on the slopes of Mt. Ellinitisa⁵¹ or, farther to the north, in the area of Mt. Tetrazi.⁵²

At around the same time as the Messenian arbitration (most probably between 180 and 170 BCE), two different panels made up respectively of Milesian and Rhodian judges were mobilised to deliver a sentence concerning a disputed area between Hermione and Epidauros, both members of the Achaean League.⁵³ As a matter of fact, this evidence (Moretti, *ISE I 43*) yields us the earliest official proclamation of a *koine chora* by an established authority ([κα]τὰ τὰδε ἐπέκριναν καὶ συνέλυσαν οἱ Μιλήσιοι δικασταὶ ... εἶναι ταύτην [*scil. χώραν*] κοινὴν Ἑρμιονέων καὶ Ἐπιδαυρίων).⁵⁴ The submission of a dispute to authorities outside the League was clearly a concrete tool in the hands of the opponents, as the involvement of a Milesian δικαστήριον in the arbitration between Messene and Megalopolis demonstrates.⁵⁵

46 A topographical study on the contents of *SEG 58, 370*, which Rousset has hoped for (in *BE 2013*, No. 153), has been undertaken in Pikoulas, 2010-2013.

47 Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012, p. 526; Pikoulas, 2010-2013, p. 270-272.

48 Themelis, 2008, p. 215-216; Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012, p. 526. For the πόλις Πυλωνέων in *SEG 11, 979*, l. 23 (2nd or 1st cent. BCE), see Themelis, 2008, p. 216; Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012, p. 522-523 (who posit the location of the ancient site around modern *Kato Melpēia*); Pikoulas, 2010-2013, p. 268-269.

49 It is worth noticing that an unpublished passage that reproduces the πρόκλησις of the Megalopolitans is reported to refer to the τέρμονες of the *Akreiatis* (ll. 119-120); see Thür, 2012, p. 301-302; Pikoulas, 2010-2013, p. 272.

50 For a different view, see Pikoulas, 2010-2013, p. 272.

51 Themelis, 2008, p. 215.

52 Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012, p. 527; Pikoulas, 2010-2013, p. 272.

53 The text of this κρίμα is preserved by two copies, the one found in Epidauros (*IG IV² 1, 75+* = *SEG 31, 328*), the other from Hermione (*SEG 11, 377 + 51, 431*). Both are re-edited and commented by Moretti, 1967, p. 100-105 (Moretti, *ISE I 43* = *SEG 25, 375*); Ager, 1996, p. 170-173 (No. 63), Magnetto, 1997, p. 405-416 (No. 69) and Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 72-80 (No. 10). A likely chronology for this judgement has been offered by Dixon, 2001 (= *SEG 51, 431*; 175-172 BCE), based on prosopography of some Rhodian judges appearing in *IG IV² 1, 75*, fr. B, ll. 25-28 and Polyb. XXVIII 7, 9.

54 Moretti, *ISE I 43*, ll. 1-2, 15.

55 Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012, p. 539-540.

The dispute in Argolis was triggered by a legal challenge (πρόκλησις) by the Hermioneans to the Epidaurians, who also shared the decision to entrust the two boards with the survey of the contested borderland.⁵⁶ Milesians and Rhodians issued an unanimous verdict, proclaiming as κοινή χώρα the territory that embraced the river Sellas (to the east), the Wild Harbours and Cape Strouthous (to the west). This plot of land, which is said to be a part of a larger area called Διδυμία, was delimited by two parallel sequences of topographical points of reference, one coastal, the other inland.⁵⁷ The latter overlaps in reverse order a route sketched out by Pausanias, who also attests to the existence of a locality named Δίδυμοι in this area.⁵⁸ The demarcation is rather precise and, as frequently happens, it results from a combination of both natural and artificial limits.⁵⁹ As Clémence Weber-Pallez has pointed out, however, boundary stones and other landmarks placed to distinguish an internal border between Argolic communities do not have to be understood as elements of a 'linear' frontier, but they dot the landscape often disregarding sub-regions of cross-border cooperation and exchange, as the territories of the later proclaimed *koinai chorai* were.⁶⁰

In the century preceding the Roman Conquest and the establishment of the province of Achaëa, the Argolic Ἀκτὴ appears to have been swept by other interpolis controversies and, accordingly, undergone significant border changes.⁶¹ Besides the territorial dispute between Epidauros and Hermione, conflicts on the northern side of the peninsula flared up between Epidauros and Corinth and – later – between Troezen and Arsinoë/Methana.⁶² In particular, the terms of the latter conflict are preserved in the *homologia* engraved on a stele from Epidauros (*SEG* 55, 425)⁶³ and in another fragmentary copy found in Troezen (*SEG* 55, 418).⁶⁴ The agreement was fostered by a Lagid king, most probably Ptolemy VI (181/0-146/5), while compliance with the provisions was entrusted to the Athenians, allies of the Ptolemies.⁶⁵ Troezen, a member of the Achaean League at that time, and Arsinoë/Methana, a *polis* under

56 On the πρόκλησις, see Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 75 and Cassayre, 2010, p. 234, 243.

57 On the identification of the topographical references mentioned in these inscriptions, see esp. Jameson, 1953, p. 160-167, Moretti, 1967, p. 102-104 and Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 78-80. For a state-of-art, see also Dixon, 2000, p. 157-166.

58 Paus. II 36, 3.

59 Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 57-58, 159. On the description and representation of spaces and distances in Greek arbitration inscriptions, see Matijašić, 2022 (esp. p. 397-398 for the arbitration between Hermione and Epidauros).

60 Weber-Pallez, 2016 (esp. p. 60).

61 Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 157.

62 For the dispute between Epidauros and Corinth (ca. 242-238 BCE), which was mediated by Megarian judges, see *IG* IV² 1, 70-71, with some commentary in Ager, 1996, p. 113-117 (No. 38); Magnetto, 1997, p. 212-224 (No. 36); Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 16-23 (No. 3); cf. also Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 156-159.

63 The text provided by the *Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum* reproduces the revised edition of *IG* IV² 1, 76-77 in Carusi, 2005, p. 93-95. Cf. Ager, 1996, p. 381-385 (No. 138); Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 97-109 (No. 12).

64 For the revised edition *IG* IV 741, see again Carusi, 2005, p. 86-87.

65 For the chronological frame of this agreement, see Carusi, 2005, p. 126-136. For some prosopographic remarks and the uncommon name Γνίκων (*SEG* 55, 425, l. 3), see Dixon, 2000, p. 222-224. On the

Ligid control, came into conflict over a border zone, which included at least four territories named Στενίτας, Διαστενίτις, Χερσονάσος and Πραξωνεῖον. Toponymy makes the location of the contested area immediately transparent: the two *poleis* mainly contended for the possession of the thin strip of land connecting the Methana-Peninsula with the Peloponnesian mainland.⁶⁶ Other contiguous plots of land outside the isthmus might have been involved in the dispute, but the damages of the stone make the text not fully clear on this point. Due to the poor condition of the stone, however, one can only be certain that Στενίτας was proclaimed κοινός,⁶⁷ while the other sub-regions did not enjoy the same status assuredly.⁶⁸ The limits of the *koine chora* were outlined in a fragmentary passage of the *homologia* and included a fortified work (χάραξ) and some private estates.⁶⁹

The reconsideration of the epigraphic evidence sheds light on some geographical characteristics of the *koinai chorai*. First, the establishment of common territories concerns the borderlands of three Peloponnesian regions so far: Arcadia, Messenia and Argolis.⁷⁰ Secondly, the extension of these *chorai* is quite hard to assess, but in the only two ‘measurable’ examples it appears to be uneven: if we look at the disputes in Argolis, we are dealing with an area of relevant dimensions (*koine chora* of Epidauros and Hermione) and another relatively small (the isthmus of the Methana-Peninsula).⁷¹ Third, the physical configuration of a *koine*

history of Methana, the Ptolemaic control of the peninsula and the name change to Arsinoe, see Gill, Foxhall, Bowden, 1997, p. 74-75.

66 See Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 108-109; Dixon, 2000, p. 227-236; Carusi, 2005, p. 102-103.

67 *SEG* 55, 425, l. 8.

68 *SEG* 55, 425, ll. 6-8; see Carusi, 2005, p. 102, 107. There are other fragmentary references to a common region (ll. 24, 34), as well as to common income from tuna fishing (ll. [24], 39, 43/44, 49). For the latter point, see below.

69 *SEG* 55, 425, ll. 20-27. On the nature of this fortification, which could be linked to the τείχη or the φρούριον in Thuc. IV, 45, 2, see again Gill, Foxhall, Bowden, 1997, p. 74-75, followed by Dixon, 2000, p. 229-230 and Carusi, 2005, p. 107-108. On the private estates in the *koine chora* and on the issues of legal nature they raise, see Carusi, 2005, p. 109.

70 Another possible testimony concerning an area of joint exploitation in Arcadia might be the arbitration between Alipheira and Lepreon that has been dated to 194/3 BCE (*IPark* 26 = *SEG* 25, 449; for some commentary, see Ager, 1996, p. 226-228 [No. 82]; Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 41-46 [No. 6]). The word πολύκοινος occurs in the boundary demarcation which likely follows the final part of the verdict and precedes a list of judges called for a sentence (*IPark* 26, l. 25: [--]σιν τὰν πολύκοινο[ν]). The poor condition of the inscription and the lack of a clear context do not allow us to speculate much on the existence of an area of shared exploitation between the territories of Alipheira and Lepreon. However, the presence of a (border)land ‘common to many’ (alluding perhaps even to other communities besides Alipheirans and Lepreatai) has been suggested by Laurent Dubois (1986, II, p. 253: « s’agirait-il d’une ἐσχαιά commune à plusieurs cites ? »; cf. Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 46).

71 According to Paus. II 36, 3, the inner route connecting the Cape *Strouthous* (modern *Kavo Iri*) with *Philanorion* (*Phournoi*?) – both being the opposite limits of the territory disputed between Epidauros and Hermione – was about 250 stadia long (ca. 50 km), a distance that has been rightly regarded by scholars as exaggerated (see below for further considerations). According to Ps. Scylax 50 (mid-4th century), the shoreline under Epidaurian control stretched for 30 stadia (more than 5,5 km) along the Argolic Gulf and the coastline from the territory of Argos to Halieis (mod. *Porto Cheli*) amounted to 100 stadia (ca. 20 km). On the other hand, the dispute between Methana and Troezen mainly

chora may vary similarly from territory to territory: the common regions known so far are sometimes landlocked, sometimes coastal; they may lie on plains, hills or mountains. In fact, the physical characteristics of these common territories seem to be subordinate to key factors that explain the reasons why these areas fell into contention from time to time: indeed, these areas turned out to be more and more attractive for some regional players not only for the possibility to exploit economic resources and commodities locally available, but also for the presence of strategic key zones or spots like isthmuses, strongholds (whether natural or not), landing places or crossroads.⁷²

4. Choronymy

The natural features of landscape inform the toponymy of a given area very frequently.⁷³ Examples from the Greek world are countless, and it is nearly impossible to draw a list of them. The borderlands under consideration are no exception. If one leaves aside the agreement between Phigaleians and Messenians in which no place names occur, all other evidence displays a toponymy overwhelmingly based on the natural characteristics of the region. Indeed, toponymy does not only provide a rough representation of a particular area, but it may turn out to be crucial to figure out the resources available in there and/or the ways of their exploitation by the locals.⁷⁴

In general terms, the *koinai chorai* of the Peloponnese cannot always be identified through a choronym unambiguously. They are sometimes part of a larger region, as happens for the common areas between Epidaurus and Hermione (unnamed, but included in the *Didymia*),⁷⁵ or they are made up of more sub-regional entities (each with its own denomination), as happens for the Messenian-Megalopolitan borderlands and, likely, for the common areas around the

concerned the thin strip of land that binds the volcanic peninsula of Methana with the mainland (1,3 km long × 0,3 large, according to Robert 1960b, p. 158). The other two territories mentioned in the *homologia* and perhaps pertaining to the *koine chora* (*Chersonasos* and *Praxoneion*) are likely to pinpoint at the immediate borders of the isthmus (see Carusi, 2005, p. 109: « gli elementi forniti dalla moderna toponomastica sembrano confermare che la zona oggetto dell'accordo tra le due città gravitasse intorno al sottile istmo che univa la penisola di Methana alla terraferma »).

72 The presence of a *χάραξ* on the isthmus of Methana is just one example of the military importance that a given territory could assume for the control of a larger region. From the strategic point of view, on the other hand, one can consider the importance of the route connecting Messene and Megalopolis: passing through the areas under contention in *SEG* 58, 370, this route gave access to the Messenian lowlands and, further beyond, to the Western coast of the Peloponnese through the *Aulon* of Messenia (Strab. VIII 3, 25; Paus. IV 36, 7). Just a few years before the events of *SEG* 58, 370, for instance, the same route was likely followed by the Achaean στρατηγός Diophanes to launch assaults on Messene in order to restore the city under Achaean control (summer 191 BCE; see Liv. XXXVI 31, 1-5). What is more, a meeting between Flamininus and Diophanes took place at Andania, where the Achaeans were warned not to attack Messenians anymore (Liv. XXXVI 31, 7-8).

73 See for example Schmitt, 1995, p. 633-634.

74 Perono Cacciafoco, Cavallaro, 2023, p. 134-137.

75 Moretti, *ISE* I 43, ll. 15-16: εἶναι ταύτην (*scil.* χάραν) κοινήν Ἑρμιονέων καὶ Ἐπιδαυρίων | οὖσαν τῆς Διδυμίας κτλ.

isthmus of Methana. If one extends the chronological horizon of the evidence discussed here, it may be observed that the two common areas of Arcadia which are mentioned in the border demarcation from Orchomenos are named after the vegetation (Παδόεσσα; Ἀρία).⁷⁶

Place names drawn from landscape features are originally conceived by locals and, as such, imply local inter-community and cross-border dynamics.⁷⁷ Even if a given borderland may be known under different denominations depending on the different regional frequenters,⁷⁸ landscape toponymy can be ‘objective’ enough to describe and represent a specific region with no need of other equivalence.⁷⁹ In this respect, the ‘isthmus’ denominations of the disputed territories in the *homologia* between Troezen and Arsinoe/Methana (*Stenos*, *Diastenos*, *Chersonasos*) are enlightening, as it is the choronym *Akreiatis* in the epigraphic dossier from Messene. The latter overtly alludes to an upland area subject to joint exploitation, lying somewhere on the north-eastern fringes of the Messenian territory. Similarly, the dispute between Epidauros and Hermione provides a great variety of place names alluding to distinctive shapes or qualities of the territory, like the two peaks of Mt. Didyma or the availability of landing places in the Ἄγριοι Λιμένες.⁸⁰ In most cases, the very effectiveness of these denominations has produced a toponymic persistence that makes the identification of the ancient topographical reference points easier.⁸¹

In other occasions, however, toponymy is less straightforward. Even natural place names turn out to be elusive for us when looking at landmarks like the Ἄκραι κολούραι in the inland of Hermione. The westernmost limit of the *koine chora* between Epidauros and Hermione owed its name to sparrows (Cape Στρουθοῦς),⁸² while one of the territories at stake in the dispute between Messene and Megalopolis (Βιπειᾶτις) might be associated with a grazing area tentatively.⁸³ Scholarship refers eponymic place names like Πραξωνεῖον or Φιλανόρεια/

76 *IPark* 14, ll. 18-19, 22-23; cf. Daverio Rocchi, 1988, p. 98.

77 For some general remarks concerning the study of toponymy, see Taylor, 2016 and Hough, 2016. For the relationships between toponymy and landscape in a comparative perspective, see Perono Cacciafoco, Cavallaro, 2023, p. 134-157. For toponymy and natural habitat in the ancient world, see Daverio Rocchi, 2016, p. 73.

78 For some examples of interchangeable place names from the area of Mycale (Κάριον/Χάραξ; Θίνχος πάγος/οἱ κατὰ Σανίδειαν τόποι), see Carusi, 2003, p. 147-149.

79 A useful classification based on the practices of place-naming can be found in Blair, Tent, 2021. On the practical function of landscape toponymy, see Perono Cacciafoco, Cavallaro, 2023, p. 136 (« Toponyms, by alluding to and describing the related landscapes, helped people to orientate themselves in the spaces and, in the absence of drawing tools and writing systems, facilitated the sketching of a mental, oral, and ideal map of their territory »).

80 See also Hesych. s.v. Ἄγριοι λιμένες [α 803 Latte]; cf. Wilhelm, 1911 [1974].

81 J. and L. Robert in *BE* 1949, No. 68 and *BE* 1954, No. 116; Jameson, 1953, p. 161-165; Moretti, 1967, p. 103-104. A similar toponymic persistence may be observed for the territory corresponding to the *koine chora* between Troezen and Methana (see Robert, 1960b, p. 159-160; Rousset, 2003-2004, p. 120; Carusi, 2005, p. 102-103).

82 See also Paus. II 36, 3.

83 See already Thür, 2012, p. 299 (« In the course of the dispute it [*scil.* the Akreiatis] became connected with Bipeiatis, most probably unfertile pastureland close by or surrounding it »). For some more consideration on Bipeiatis, see below in Appendix.

Φιλανόριον to individuals or heroes, whose memory is lost to us.⁸⁴ Finally, an eminently artificial nature informs the border shaped by the so-called βολέοι λίθοι, where piles of stones punctuated the southeasternmost (?) limits of the *koine chora* between Epidauros and Hermione.⁸⁵

Perhaps nothing is more local than landscape toponymy. Indeed, place names deriving from natural environment mirror first and foremost a local level of landscape perception and representation and, as such, they can be regarded as an authentic expression of an emic point of view. After all, city decrees themselves are informed by an emic perspective, being documents that stem from the heart of one community. In the texts addressed to city audiences, an extensive description of locally known micro-regions may be replaced by local toponyms that could have a very limited circulation in other parts of the Greek world and even lesser attestation in our sources, if any. The regional toponymy occurring in the dispute between Messene and Megalopolis can be an enlightening example of this metonymic use of place names. In general terms, the evidence under examination presupposes some sort of agreement by the different parties in the use of local toponymy. When going back over the history of the dispute against Megalopolis, the Messenian *dossier* reproduces the geography of this long-lasting conflict according to local place names, and both the Megalopolitan counterpart and the different courts called for a judgement seem to conform to that toponymy.⁸⁶ The

84 For the *Praxoneion*, see Carusi, 2005, p. 103; for *Philanoreia* or *Philanorion* (Paus. II 36, 3), see Wilhelm, 1948, p. 72-73.

85 See Paus. II 36, 3: ἀπό Μάσητος δὲ ὁδὸς ἐν δεξιᾷ ἐστὶν ἐπὶ ἄκρην καλουμένην Στρουθοῦντα. Στάδιοι δὲ ἀπὸ τῆς ἄκρας ταύτης κατὰ τῶν ὄρων τὰς κορυφὰς πενήκοντά εἰσι καὶ διακόσιοι ἐς Φιλανόριον τε καλούμενον καὶ ἐπὶ Βολεούς· οἱ δὲ Βολεοὶ οὗτοι λίθων εἰσι σωροὶ λογάδων (« From Mases there is a road on the right to a headland called Struthous [Sparrow Peak]. From this headland by way of the summits of the mountains the distance to the place called Philanorium and to the Boleoi is two hundred and fifty stades. These Boleoi are heaps of unhewn stones. »; transl. W.H.S. Jones). For the distance of 250 stades, see the emendation proposed by Wilhelm, 1948, p. 79 (55 stades).

86 SEG 58, 370, ll. 29-33: ..., ἀποδόντες οἱ Μεγαλοπολιταὶ ὄρους Ἀπολλωνίδαι τῶι στραταγῶι τᾶς τε Ἐνδανικᾶς | καὶ Πυλανικᾶς καὶ τᾶς Ἀκρειάτιος καὶ | Βιπειάτιος, ... (« and the Megalopolitans gave the στραταγός Apollonidas the borders of the territories of Endania and Pyllana and of Akreiatia and Bipeiatia, ... »); ll. 39-43: καὶ γενομένης (i.e.: τῶν δικαστῶν) | [ἐν] τῶι Καρνειασίῳ δικαιολογίας ἐπὶ | [δύο ἡ]μέρας μεθ' ὕδατος, ἀπὸ μὲν τᾶς | [Ἀκρειά]τιος καὶ Βιπειάτιος ἀποστάντων | τῶν Μεγαλοπολιτῶν (« and after in the Karneiasion a debate took place over two days, with speakers' time measured by water-clock, the Megalopolitans renounced Akreiatia and Bipeiatia »); ll. 48-50: ἀμῶν δὲ συ[--- ca. 9-10 --- κρῖ]σιν ποτὶ τε Καλιάτας | [καὶ Μεγαλοπολιτ]ας περὶ τᾶς Ἀκρειάτιος | [καὶ Βιπειάτιος] ... (« and since we agreed to be judged against the Megalopolitans and the Kaliatai regarding Akreiatia and Bipeiatia ... »); ll. 52-56: Μεγαλοπολιτῶν | [μὲν? --- ca. 11 --- ὅτι] Ἀκρειάτις | καὶ Βιπειάτις Ἀρκαδία εἶ[τη καὶ] Μεγαλοπολιτῆς, ἀμῶν δὲ δι[δ]ασκόντων ὅτι Μεσσανία εἶη (« the Megalopolitans [argued] that Akreiatia and Bipeiatia were Arkadian and Megalopolitan, and we showed that they are Messenian »), ll. 61-64: κρινάντων Μεσσανίαν εἶ[μεν τὰν] χώραν τὰν Ἀκρειάτιν καὶ | Βιπειάτιν κατὰ τοὺς ὄρους οὓς ἀπειδόκαμες τοῖς κοινοῖς δαμοργοῖς (« [in a court of 147 judges], who judged that Akreiatia and Bipeiatia were Messenian according to the borders we had indicated to the common δαμοργοί »); ll. 71-73: ἀμὲ προεκαλέσατο ἅ πόλις τῶν Μεγαλοπολιτῶν περὶ τᾶς Ἀκρειάτιος χώρας (« the polis of the Megalopolitans challenged us again to undergo a judgment regarding the Akreiatia territory »); ll. 79-84: καὶ εἰσαγαγόντων (i.e.

interpolis agreement following the dispute between Troezen and Methana, on the other hand, was engraved on stelae set up in two prominent sanctuaries of the region, the *Asklepieion* of Epidauros and the temple of Poseidon at Kalaureia, as well as in the sanctuary of Athena at Athens.⁸⁷ This led once again to the conclusion that the toponymy employed for the *koine chora* of Epidauros-Hermione was freely accepted and shared by both disputants, as well as by the courts of foreign judges that were asked for an intervention. All in all, even though some pieces of evidence imply the intervention of external actors for the resolution of disputes, the etic point of view is never predominant, and no toponymic equivalence was therefore required for the demarcation of the *koinai chorai*.⁸⁸

5. Resources

For the sake of cohesion, federal organisations undertook every attempt to defuse internal or cross-border tensions on the local level and to prevent larger repercussions on the regional scale. In this respect, the case of the Achaean *koinon*, which laid down the resolution of ongoing controversies as a prerequisite for joining the League, is undoubtedly the most well-known and most revealing one.⁸⁹ In consideration of the scanty evidence available, the establishment of a *koine chora* appears not to be an obvious response for settling border conflicts. One of the reasons explaining the recourse to this tool may lie in the roots of the dispute itself and, indeed, in claims of economic nature that surface in all the texts at issue. In our case studies, economic attractiveness and resource availability are deeply embedded into every episode of border conflict in one way or another.

As the occurrences of the key terms καρπίζεσθαι, καρποί and ἐπικαρπία suggest, the exploitation of agricultural resources triggered or exacerbated the controversies under examination.⁹⁰ Since the *homologia* between Phigaleia and Messene (ca. 240 BCE), the different pieces of evidence lend emphasis on the enjoyment of land products. The decree of

τῶν κοινῶν δαμιοργῶν) εἰς τὸ | δικαστήριον τῶν Μιλησίων ἐνικά|σαμεν πάσαις ταῖς ψήφοις καθότι | εἶημεν κεκριμένοι περὶ τε ταύτας | τᾶς χώρας καὶ τᾶς Βιπειάτιος ποτῖ Μεγαλοπολίτας (« and [the common δαμιοργοί] introduced us into the court of the Milesians, we won receiving all the votes, which confirmed that we had indeed already been judged regarding this territory and the Bipeiatas against the Megalopolitans »). English translations are drawn from Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012.

87 *SEG* 55, 418, ll. 16-19 ≈ *SEG* 55, 425, ll. 53-56: οἵτινες παραγενόμενοι (ἐξ Ἀθανῶν) τὰ γεγονότα αὐτοῖς ὁμόλογα ἐπικρίναντες ἀναθεσοῦνται ἐν στάλαις εἰς τὰ ἱερά τὸ ἐγ Καλαυρεῖαι τοῦ Ποσειδᾶνος καὶ τὸ ἐν Ἐπιδάυροι τοῦ Ἀσκληπίου καὶ τὸ ἐν Ἀθήναις ἐν ἀκροπόλει τᾶς Ἀθήνας (« those who have come [from Athens] and verified the agreements between them [i.e. the Epidaurians and the Hermioneans] shall take care of the publication on stelae in the sanctuaries of Poseidon at Kalaureia and Asclepius at Epidauros and Athena on the Acropolis of Athens »; my translation).

88 Interventions of foreigners in the border disputes at issue: Aetolians in the dispute between Messenians and Phigaleians; Achaeans and a board of Milesian judges in the dispute between Messenians and Megalopolitans; Milesians and Rhodians in the contention between Epidauros and Hermione; a Lagid king in the conflict between Troezen and Arsinoe/Methana.

89 Harter-Uibopuu, 1998, p. 128-129; Mackil, 2013, p. 316-318, 361-362.

90 On the Greek vocabulary of ‘exploitation’ and its occurrence in Greek epigraphy, see esp. Robert, 1960a, p. 533-535 and also Sartre, 1979, p. 214; Fachard, 2017, p. 20.

the Messenians reproduced in the agreement with Phigaleia (*IG V 2*, 419) seems to betray the perpetuation of an extant exploitation agreement according to the same conditions as in the present.⁹¹ According to the Messenian *dossier* on the dispute with Megalopolis (*SEG 58*, 370), at some point before clashing *περὶ καρπῶν* Messenians and Megalopolitans concluded an agreement regulating the crop of *μεσόκοινοι καρποί* (literally, « half-common fruits ») in the borderlands named *Akreiatis* and *Bipeiatis*.⁹² Clauses on the revenues from land exploitation appear in both the arbitration procedure between Epidaurus and Hermione (Moretti, *ISE I 43*) and the *homologia* between Troezen and Arsinoe/Methana (*SEG 55*, 418 + *SEG 55*, 425). While the former presents a brief declaration rendering void all the charges *περὶ καρπειῶν καὶ τῶν ἐπινομῶν* (« on cropping and grazing rights ») retroactively,⁹³ the latter seeks to further discourage retroactive actions by private citizens *περὶ τᾶς ἐπικαρπίας* or *περὶ τᾶν ἐπικαρπιῶν*, providing for fines in case of violations.⁹⁴

However, land exploitation was not restricted to agricultural produce, but it also entailed other activities tied to forest economy and pasturage. In the agreement between Troezen and Arsinoe/Methana a fragmentary clause from the stone of Epidaurus is likely to refer to quarries and timber exploitation.⁹⁵ Ultimately, activities of timber cutting already appear to be the reason for the establishment of *koinai chorai* near Orchomenos. In the highlands of Arcadia, geographically landlocked and poor in cultivable plains, timber was indeed one of the resources that could grant a steady economic return.⁹⁶ The importance of the *Παδόεσσα* and *Ἄρια* and the possibility to access them for the communities involved in the delimitation procedure of *IPark 14* could have represented (or could really have been) an element of friction, which the panel of arbiters and, likely, the entire Arcadian *koinon* had

91 *IG V 1*, 419, ll. 14-16: τὰν δὲ χ[ώραν καρπ]ίξεσθαι ἑκατέρως, τὼς τε Μεσσανίω[ς] καὶ τὼς Φι[γαλείας], καθὼς καὶ νῦν καρπιζόμεθα (« The land shall be cultivated by each, [the citizens] of Messene and [those] of Phigaleia, just as we cultivated it now »; transl. S. Saba).

92 *SEG 58*, 370, ll. 65-67; cf. Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012, p. 533-534 n. 78; Youni, 2012, p. 321, 325-326; Thür, 2012, p. 300 n. 11.

93 Moretti, *ISE I 43*, ll. 20-22: Περὶ δὲ τῶν καρπειῶν καὶ τῶν ἐπινομῶν τῶν πρὸ τῆς κρίσεως μὴ εἶναι μηδετέροις ἔγκλη|μα μηθέν (« No claim is to be made concerning cropping or pasturage [which occurred] before this decision »; transl. M. H. Jameson, C. N. Runnels, T. H. van Andel).

94 *SEG 55*, 418, l. 2 + *SEG 55*, 425, l. 38. See Carusi, 2005, p. 114, who also proposes to restore κ[αρπι]ζεσθαι in l. 33 (p. 97, 112). According to Bravo, 1980, p. 866-867, the term *ἐπικαρπία* might rather be related to revenues coming from the taxation of grazing rights. However, nothing in this text hints at that explicitly.

95 *SEG 55*, 425, l. 9: [--- τᾶς] λιθίνας καὶ τᾶς ξυλίνας; see Ager, 1996, p. 384; Carusi, 2005, p. 104.

96 See Mackil, 2013, p. 276. As Rousset, 2003-2004, p. 121 has pointed out, the right to exploit wooded areas was conceded to foreigners also in the form of *ἐπιξυλία*, an accessory honour that could be awarded in proxeny decrees and that is attested in Arcadia for Orchomenos and Thisoa (*IPark 36 j, r*).

to take into account.⁹⁷ As for pasturage and transhumance,⁹⁸ the double verdict of Milesians and Rhodians suggests a significant availability of grazing lands in the territory between Epidauros and Hermione. The final clauses record that the contention originated from some kind of disagreement *περὶ τῶν ἐπινομῶν* (« about those who enjoy the grazing rights ») and, moreover, they inform us about an earlier *κρίμα περὶ τῶν αἰγῶν* (« a judgement concerning the goats ») issued over the same borderlands.⁹⁹ Similar controversies about grazing rights might have arisen in Messenia, too, if the etymology of the choronym *Bipeiatis* is intended as an allusion to the activities of husbandry and pasturage in the region.¹⁰⁰

The body of evidence shows that the access to cultivable areas and the exploitation of resources often underlay the establishment of a *koine chora*, especially in those regions of the Peloponnese where the availability of arable land was limited. Thus, land exploitation was indeed a key factor for the establishment of a *koine chora*, but certainly not the only one. If one looks at the dispute between Troezenians and Arsinoeans/Methanians, it is undeniable that the exploitation of the sea resources turns out to be an important point on the agenda of both communities. The joint exploitation of the tuna fishery, in particular, rose to relevance to such an extent that, before the double *κρίμα* of Milesians and Rhodians, the two *poleis* were able to set up a common fund based on fishery revenues (*αἱ κοιναὶ πρόσοδοι αἱ ἐκ τῶν θυννεῖων*).¹⁰¹ This fund was employed for the reparations owed to those who had suffered confiscations at the time when the borderland was proclaimed inaccessible.¹⁰² According to the interpretation of Rousset, the establishment of the *koine chora* between Troezen and

97 *IPArk* 14, ll. 27, 29. The economic interest of these common areas is proven by a couple of passages from the *Historia Plantarum* by Theophrastus, according to whom the *πηδός* was used to produce axles of chariots and drawbars of ploughs (*Hist. Plant.* V 7, 6), while the *ἄρπια* – a Doric gloss for holm-oak – was employed for the fabrication of chariot elements (*Hist. Plant.* III 16, 3). On the federal intervention of the short-lived Arcadian *koinon* in this matter, see Mackil, 2013, p. 314. The case of *IPArk* 14 forces to reconsider some statements made by Daverio Rocchi some years ago: « “[w]oodland activities” pointed to a system of skilled works that we can relate to a true woodland-economy having | its privileged space in the borderland. It was the open space where the regime of subsistence based on pasturing, hunting, gathering of spontaneous fruits, fishery from marshes and rivers, required *undivided land* and *free passage*, unlike the core plain where enclosures and farming prevailed » (Daverio Rocchi, 2016, p. 70-71, with my italics). As a matter of fact, the regulation from Arcadian Orchomenos depicts a different scenario, as also do the clauses of the agreement between the Lycians and the Termessians-near-Oenoanda concerning the ways of exploitation of Mt. Masa with the Tloeans (*SEG* 60, 1569, ll. 27-33; 160-150 BCE; see Rousset, 2010, p. 43-50). Relying on the phrasing employed in ll. 27-30 (*Τὸ δὲ Μασα ὄρος ἔστω Τλωέων, τὴν δὲ ἐπιγνέμησιν καὶ ξυλισμὸν αὐτοῦ ἐχέτωσαν Τερμησησεῖς οἱ πρὸς Οἰοάνδους εἰς τὸν ἀεὶ χρόνον*), Rousset maintains that the ownership of Mt. Masa and the right to erect buildings and populate it was assigned to the Tloeans, while the rights of pasturage and wood exploitation were granted to the Termessians exclusively (Rousset, 2010, p. 46).

98 Cf. Sartre, 1979, p. 214-215.

99 Moretti, *ISE* I 43, ll. 20-24.

100 On *Bipeiatis* in *SEG* 58, 370, see Thür, 2012, p. 299.

101 *SEG* 55, 418, ll. 6-7; *SEG* 55, 425, ll. 39 (restored), 43-44.

102 *SEG* 55, 418, ll. 5-8; *SEG* 55, 425, ll. 42-44.

Arsinoe/Methana should have taken place in a regime of shared territorial waters.¹⁰³ Against this, one might wonder if one should not rather think of land-based facilities such as tuna factories linked to fish processing.¹⁰⁴ The possibility to have access to natural landing places like the Ἄγριοι Λιμένες might also be distinguished on the background of the dispute between Epidauros and Hermione, as Magonetto has pointed out.¹⁰⁵

All in all, the economic attractiveness of these sub-regions expectedly fostered human mobility and brought into being forms of population that could cut across group identity. Such a mixed settling of borderlands and the resulting systems of joint exploitation may have developed into border conflicts whose resolution imposed a variety of possible responses by superordinate authorities. One of these responses can ultimately have been the establishment of an area of joint exploitation, i.e. a *koine chora*.

6. By Way of Conclusion. From epigraphical evidence to literary projections of the κοινὰ χῶραι

A preliminary assessment of the *koinai chorai* in the Hellenistic Peloponnese leads to a number of observations, which will profit from a closer comparison with other regions of the Greek world in the future. What can be concluded with regard to the epigraphical evidence now is that most of the sources refer to the 2nd century BCE. This may appear a pretentious conclusion if one looks at the extreme meagreness of the available documentation. However, this simple observation turns out to be of some interest if one considers a telling statistic presented by Rousset some years ago. In 1994, Rousset compiled a list of 240 inscriptions concerning ancient Greek borders: almost one third of this corpus (72 inscriptions) dates to the 2nd century BCE, while more than one eighth of it goes back to the 3rd century (33).¹⁰⁶

103 Rousset, 2003-2004, p. 120. See, in the same vein, Dixon, 2000, p. 193. Peter Funke has drawn my attention to a passage from a treaty between Acarnanians, Amphiloichians and Ambraciotai (*I.Mus. Thyrio* 2, A, II = *SEG* 63, 391 [II]; late 4th century BCE) where the parties are likely to agree on the joint exploitation of a sea loch of the Gulf of Ambracia (ll. 8-9: [--- τῶν δὲ θαλάσσης κοινῶν χρῆσθω ἕκαστος]; see Funke, Hallof, 2013, p. 58-60). From a legal point of view, however, it is worth highlighting that the applicability of the modern notion of 'territorial waters' to the ancient world is a matter of contention among legal historians and, at the end of the day, it appears to be rather problematic (against the elaboration of the notion of territorial waters by ancient jurists, see Purpura, 2008 who convincingly rejects the earlier influential position of Dumont, 1977).

104 Carusi, 2005, p. 118; Mackil, 2013, p. 317. Although Foxhall, Gill, Forbes, 1997, p. 272 and Dixon, 2000, p. 232 cited Robert, 1960b, p. 159-160 n. 2 for the alleged remains of tuna traps on the Western coast of the isthmus of Methana, I read no clear reference to this in the passage at issue (« ... je considère la baie appelée Θυννί à l'Ouest de l'isthme de Méthana comme la persistance des θυννεῖα antiques, de même que le nom du golfe de droite Steno, conserve un toponyme ancien de l'arbitrage; cela, bien que Θυννί puisse se trouver ailleurs, venant des madragues ou des guettes du thon, et qu'il y ait un cap Thynni à l'Ouest du territoire d'Hermione. »). According to Dixon, 2000, p. 232, however, remains of tuna traps « are still visible to the west of the isthmus itself and I have been told that this is the old method of fishing around Methana ».

105 Magonetto, 1997, p. 413; cf. Sartre, 1979, p. 215-216.

106 Rousset, 1994, p. 98-100.

Following Rousset's provisional compilation, it comes as no surprise that four out of five inscriptions considered in this paper date precisely to the centuries with more documentation at our disposal. The overall impression is that the Greeks perceived the *koinai chorai* as areas of economic interaction, animated overwhelmingly by local networks. Borrowing the words of Emily Mackil, « [t]he ancient evidence, both literary and numismatic, points to economic cooperation between poleis within a region prior to the development of formal state institutions at the regional level, which will suggest that economic considerations were part of the federal bargain from the start ». ¹⁰⁷ Before the right to exploit a given region was proclaimed or granted, and before the 'common' status of these borderlands was formalised, these common regions and micro-regions had presumably been areas of cross-border frequentation for a long time – and not only for economic exchange. The continuity and – so to speak – density of these exchanges probably recommended the establishment of common regions, precisely where a rigid demarcation of the border and a clear-cut definition of interpolis boundaries were objectively unfeasible. With regard to neighbourhood relations between *poleis*, the pragmatism of some communities is sometimes foreshadowed on the mythical and religious level. The friendly relations between Phigaleians and Messenians, for instance, took the shape of intermarriage in the Messenian tradition reworking the archaic struggles against Sparta: according to a story elaborated most likely during the 3rd century, Hagnagora, the sister of the Messenian king Aristomenes, was bestowed in marriage to Tharyx, the king of Phigaleia. ¹⁰⁸ Similarly, the picture of Troezenia as a space of (interpolis) confrontation echoes the mythical division of the region between Athena and Poseidon after a duel with no winner. ¹⁰⁹ From a religious point of view, the projection of troublesome neighbourly relations materialises in the worship of Apollo *Horios* at Hermione, whose cult is recorded by Pausanias to preserve the memory of a border conflict. ¹¹⁰ The attitude of the Orchomenians for the establishment of sharing places with their neighbours surfaces in the border sanctuary of Artemis *Hymnia*, common to Orchomenians and Mantineans. ¹¹¹ These are just a few examples linked to some of the communities considered in this paper. It would not be surprising if other literary evidence, which implies the notion of border in one way or another, could be reinterpreted in the light of data stemming from the *koinai chorai* around the Greek world.

Appendix

The place name Βπειῶτις

As observed by Ilias N. Arnaoutoglu and Luraghi/Magnetto the place name Βπειῶτις discloses some dialectal colour. ¹¹² The change $\text{ϕ} > \beta$ is well attested for the Laconian dialect,

¹⁰⁷ Mackil, 2013, p. 246.

¹⁰⁸ Paus. IV 24, 1 (likely connected to Rhian. *BNJ* 265 F 40).

¹⁰⁹ Paus. II 30, 6.

¹¹⁰ Paus. II 35, 2.

¹¹¹ Paus. VIII 13, 1.

¹¹² Arnaoutoglu, 2009-2010, p. 184 n. 10; Luraghi, Magnetto, 2012, p. 526-527.

especially at the beginning of a word.¹¹³ On the other hand, the pertinence of the anthroponym Βίππος to this group is highly uncertain.¹¹⁴ If one assumes that the form Βπειῖτις can be in fact a degeminated form for Βπ(π)ειῖτις, the possibility that this obscure choronym must be somehow related to (a grazing area of) horses cannot be ruled out. Like the change φ > β, cases of degeminated forms in Laconian are well attested too and, as for -ππ- > -π-, they are overwhelmingly tied to the word ἵππος and its compounds.¹¹⁵ A passage from the Platonic *Alcibiades I* (122d), whose fictional background has to be fixed around 430 BCE, may suggest some kind of connection between the Spartan horse husbandry and the large availability of grazing areas in Messenia.¹¹⁶ This evidence, however, appears to be less conclusive than one might be led to believe. Interestingly, the stele preserving the victory list of the Spartan Damonon refers to chariot races held in the perioecic settlement of Thouria in Messenia in the framework of the local Ποιοῖδα.¹¹⁷ Finally, it is worth noticing that a late Hellenistic inscription from Messene attests to the existence of groups called ἵπποτρόφοι καὶ νεώτεροι, who were led by a ἀγέμων and performed perhaps some military duties.¹¹⁸

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113 See for example *IG V 1*, 864-865 for Βορθεῖα (2nd cent. BCE), but also *IG V 1*, 1277, l. 4 (2nd/1st cent.?) with Buck, 1955, p. 47 (for the compound Λαβίπτα).

114 Polyb. XXIII, 18, 3; XXIV, 1, 6; 2, 4. See Bechtel, 1917, p. 93 for Βίππος < Βί-ιππος (based on βία, « violence »); cf. *LGPN III.a s.v.* Βίππος (2nd cent. BCE).

115 A case in point is again Λαβίπτα for Λαβίπτα in *IG V 1*, 1277, l. 4; see Hermann, 1923, p. 187-188; Vessella, 2018, p. 108 and 111.

116 Hodkinson, 1990, p. 153-154.

117 *IG V 1*, 213, ll. 18-22; for a date to ca. 400-390 BCE, see Nafissi, 2013, p. 114-117. For Spartan hippotrophy, see Chandezon, 2014, p. 37-39.

118 *SEG 47*, 393; 1st cent. BCE.

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